

Development And Characterization of Sublingual Film Containing Ropinirole Hydrochloride.

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ABSTRACT

The present work aimed at preparing mouth dissolving films (MDFs) of Ropinirole Hydrochloride with the purpose of developing a dosage form for a very quick onset of action, which is very convenient for administration, without the problem of swallowing and using water. The films of Ropinirole Hydrochloride were prepared by using polymers such as Hydroxy Propyl Methyl Cellulose (HPMC E-15) and Polyethylene Glycol (PEG-400) as plasticizer, by a solvent casting method for treatment of Parkinson disease. HPMC E-15 used as film forming agent were developed from the range of concentration (50 mg – 600 mg) and PEG-400 used as plasticizer developed range of concentration (0.3-1 ml) for solvent casting method. Thus, the optimized concentration of film forming agent was (400 mg) and plasticizer concentration was (0.7ml). By using optimized concentration, Ropinirole Hydrochloride MDFs were prepared by adding other excipients. The formulated mouth dissolving films (MDFs) were evaluated for physical characteristics such as uniformity of weight, thickness, folding endurance, drug content uniformity, percentage elongation, and tensile strength, and gave satisfactory results. The formulations were subjected to disintegration, *In-vitro* drug release studies. The FTIR and DSC studies revealed that no physicochemical interaction between excipients and drug. A marked increase in the % drug release was exhibited by mouth dissolving films of Ropinirole Hydrochloride containing HPMC E-15 as a polymer at below 1 min. when compared to other polymers films. Mouth dissolving film of Ropinirole Hydrochloride containing HPMC E-15 as polymer showed 97.66 % drug release at 30 min. Mouth dissolving films of Ropinirole Hydrochloride containing HPMC E-15 showed better tensile strength (70.56 ± 0.9 g/mm²), Percentage elongation (33.33 ± 2.88 %), folding endurance (168 ± 2.081 No. of folds), *in-vitro* disintegration time (35 ± 3.511 sec.), thickness (0.4 ± 0.17 mm)..

Keywords: Ropinirole Hydrochloride, Film, drug release, *In-vitro*.

INTRODUCTION

Since time immemorial, oral drug administration has been one of the most convenient and widely accepted routes of delivery for most therapeutic agents. Traditionally, oral dosage forms refer to tablets, capsules, and liquid preparations taken orally, swallowed and transiting the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) for post buccal absorption. For the last few decades, researchers have been developing intraoral delivery systems (IODS) that can produce desirable drug exposure for optimum therapeutic effect. The intraoral dosage form includes fast dissolving dosage forms (Tablets, Films, Wafers), sublingual tablets,

buccal/ gingival patches, microparticles, Periodontal fibres, solutions and sprays, chewing gums, dry powders, topical gels, topical pastes, bioadhesive tablets, topical ointments, local injections, dissolvable lozenge. The market for intraoral drug delivery products has undergone a period of innovation and significant expansion over the past decade. The main driver of this market growth is the fast dissolve prescription and Over the Counter market segments. Fast dissolving drug delivery systems were first developed in the late 1970s as an alternative to tablets, capsules and syrups for people experiencing difficulty in swallowing traditional solid dosage forms. This new and novel oral drug delivery system dissolves or

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disperses quickly in few seconds after placement in the mouth without water can alleviate the problem of swallowing tablets. This fast-dissolving system includes tablets, caplets, granules, films, wafers and powders. The United States provides the greatest market opportunity for fast dissolve dosage forms followed by Europe and Japan. The film is an ideal intraoral fast-dissolving drug delivery system, which satisfies the unmet needs of the market, is easy to handle and administer, maintains a simple and convenient packaging, alleviates unpleasant taste, and is straightforward to manufacture. The film is placed on the top or the floor of the tongue. It is retained at the site of application and rapidly releases the active agent for local and/or systemic absorption. (Vaidya M. M. *et al.*, 2013).

A new oral fast dissolving dosage form such as the fast-dissolving tablet or fast dissolving film has been developed which offers the combined advantages of ease of dosing and convenience of dosing in the absence of water or fluid.

The mucosal membranes of the oral cavity can be divided into five regions: The floor of the mouth (sublingual), the buccal mucosa (cheeks), the gums (gingiva), the palatal mucosa, and the lining of the lips. These oral mucosal regions are different from each other in terms of anatomy, permeability to drug, and their ability to retain a system for a desired length of time. Although the buccal mucosa is less permeable than the sublingual mucosa (Amir *et al.*, 1998) within the oral mucosal cavity, delivery of drugs is classified into three categories,

1. Sublingual delivery

This is systemic delivery of drugs through the mucosal membranes lining the floor of the mouth.

2. Buccal delivery

This is the drug administration through the mucosal membranes lining the cheeks (buccal mucosa)

3. Local delivery

This is drug delivery into the oral cavity. In addition, the sublingual route has general advantages over other

delivery routes, such as nasal, pulmonary, oral and transdermal systems. (Amir *et al.*, 1998)

1.1 Recent Trends in Oral Drug Delivery

Recently Mouth dissolving film (MDF) is one of the most widely used as commercial product in market because quick onset of action, fast dissolving, and fast disintegrating in few seconds etc. therefore MDF is widely used for local anesthetics for toothaches, headache, body pain, migraine, hypertension, oral ulcers, cold sores and treatment of psychological disease. However, those films are preferable over mouth dissolving tablets in terms of flexibility and comfort. In addition, they can circumvent the relatively short residence time of oral gels on the mucosa, which are easily washed and removed by saliva. Moreover, fast dissolving films are also suitable for protecting wound surfaces, thus reducing pain also could treat oral diseases more effectively and increasing the treatment effectiveness. An ideal Mouth dissolving film should be flexible, elastic, soft yet adequately strong to withstand breakage due to stress from mouth activities. It should be non-irritant, do not cause teeth discoloration, resist metabolic barrier, and be capable of releasing a drug at appropriate rate, swelling of film, if exists should not be too extensive to prevent discomfort. (Chyein Y. *et al.*, 2012)

1.2 Overview of Oral Mucosa

Drug delivery via the oral mucosa is a promising route, when one wishes to achieve a rapid onset of action or improved bioavailability for drugs with high first-pass metabolism. Thus, there is a growing interest in developing alternative dosage forms, i.e. orally fast disintegrating strip, which allow a rapidly dissolving drug to absorb directly into the systemic circulation through the oral mucosa. These kinds of dosage forms are also convenient for children, elderly patients with swallowing difficulties, and in the absence of potable liquids. However, in addition to formulation considerations, the properties of the active compound have to be appropriate in order to achieve drug delivery into systemic circulation after intraoral administration. The oral mucosa is composed of an outermost layer of stratified squamous epithelium below this lies a basement membrane, a lamina propria followed by the

submucosa as the innermost layer. (Patil S. L. *et al.*, 2012)

Classification of Oral Films

There are three different subtypes of oral films (Kaur M. *et al.*, 2013)

1. Flash release
2. Mucoadhesive melt-away wafer
3. Mucoadhesive sustained-release wafers

Table 1. Classification of Oral Films (Raghavendrarao N.G.*et al.*, 2013)

Property/Sub Type	Flash Release	Water Mucoadhesive Melt-Away Wafer	Mucoadhesive Sustained Release Wafer
Area (cm ²) Thickness (μm) Structure	2-8 20-70 Single Layer	2-7 50-500 Single or Multi-Layer System	2-4 50-250 Multi Layer System
Excipient	Soluble, highly hydrophilic polymer	Soluble, hydrophilic polymer	Low or on Soluble Polymer
Drug Phase	Solid Solution	Solid Solution or Suspended drug particle	Suspension or Solid Solution
Application	Tongue (upper palate)	Gingival or Buccal Region	Gingival (Other region in oral cavity)
Dissolution	Maximum 60 sec	Disintegrate in few min. forming gel	Maximum 8-10 hrs

1.3. Evaluation Parameters of Oral Fast Dissolving Films (MDFs)

1.3.1. Organoleptic Evaluations

Color is a vital means of identification for many pharmaceutical products and is also usually important for consumer acceptance. The colour of the product must be uniform within a dosage form. Odour is also important for consumer acceptance of oral dosage forms and can provide an indication of the quality of oral strips or films as the quality of oral strips or films as the presence of an odour in a batch could indicate a stability problem. However, his presence of an odour may be characteristic of the drug added ingredients. Utilize taste panels to judge the preference of different flavours and flavour levels in the development of a product. Taste preference is however subjective and the control of taste in the production of oral soluble

films is usually based on the presence or absence of a specified taste. (Bhura N. *et al.*, 2012)

1.3.2. Tensile Strength

Tensile strength is the maximum stress applied to a point at which the strip specimen breaks 14. It is calculated by the applied load at rupture divided by the cross-sectional area of the strip as given in the equation below, (Herrero A. M. *et al.*, 2007)

$$\frac{\text{Rupture force}}{\text{Length} \times \text{Thickness}}$$

1.3.3. % Elongation (Amin A. *et al.*, 2011)

$$\frac{L - L_0}{L_0} \times 100$$

1.3.4 Folding endurance

Folding endurance is determined by repeated folding of the strip at the same

Place till the strip breaks. The number of times the film is folded without breaking is

Computed as the folding endurance value. (Patil *et al.*, 2014)

1.3.5 Disintegration time

Disintegration of orally fast dissolving films requires USP disintegration apparatus. The disintegration time limit of 60 seconds or less for orally disintegrating tablets described in CDER guidance can be applied to fast dissolving oral strips. Disintegration time will vary depending on the formulation but typically the disintegration ranges from 20 to 50 seconds. Although, no official guidance is available for oral fast disintegrating films strips. (Yellanki S. K. *et al.*, 2011)

1.3.6. *In vitro* drug release

Dissolution studies of films were performed by USP type II apparatus in 6.8phosphate buffer (500ml) and 0.1N HCl (500ml). The temperature ($37\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$) and the rotation speed was 50 rpm. The samples were withdrawn at various time intervals and analysed

spectrophotometrically. (Arya A. *et al.*, 2010 and Sharma R. *et al.*, 2010)

1.3.7. Content Uniformity

The test for the content uniformity is carried out taking a sample film of size $2\times 2\text{cm}^2$ which is placed in a beaker containing 10 ml of a suitable medium. The contents were

stirred in a cyclo-mixer to dissolve the film which was transferred to a volumetric flask (10ml). The absorbance of the solution was measured against the corresponding blank solution at particular wavelength using a standard assay method described for the standard pharmacopoeia. Content uniformity is determined by estimating the API content in individual film. Limit of content uniformity is 85-115%.

1.3.8. Morphology Studies

Morphology of the prepared film can be observed under a motic electron photomicrograph. Motoc electron photomicrographs can be recorded at 100 X magnification. (Bhura N. *et al.* 2012)

2. MATERIAL & METHOD:

2.1 List of materials

Table 2. List of materials

Sr. No.	Materials	Grade	Manufacture
1	Ropinirol HCl	Analytical Grade	USV Limited, Daman
2	HPMC E 15	Analytical Grade	Colorcon pvt Ltd., Mumbai-64
3	Aspartame	Analytical Grade	Merck chem, Mumbai
4	PEG-400	Lab. Grade	Glenmark, Mumbai, India
5	Citric Acid	Lab. Grade	Lobachemie Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai
6	Vanilin	Lab. Grade	Lobachemie Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai

2.2 List of chemicals

Table 3. List of chemicals

Sr. No.	Name of Solvent	Grade	Name of Manufacture
1	Distilled Water	Analytical Grade	TIP, Paldhi-Bk
2	Hydrochloric acid	Lab. Grade	Lobachemie Pvt. Ltd, Mumbai
3	Potassium chloride	Lab. Grade	Lobachemie Pvt. Ltd, Mumbai
4	Sodium hydroxide	Lab. Grade	Merck specialties Pvt Ltd, Mumbai
5	Potassium dihydrogen phosphate	Lab. Grade	SD Fine Chem. Ltd ,Mumbai
6	Chloroform	Lab. Grade	Lobachemie Pvt. Ltd, Mumbai
7	Acetone	Lab. Grade	RFCL Limited, New Delhi.
8	Ethanol	Lab. Grade	RFCL Limited, New Delhi.
9	Methanol	Lab. Grade	Lobachemie Pvt. Ltd, Mumbai

2.3 List of Equipment's & Instrument:

Table 4. List of Equipment's / Instruments

Sr. No.	Name of Equipment's	Name of Manufacture
1	Modified Platform	Laboratory made
2	Petri dish	Borosilicate
3	Glass slide	Soyo Glasses
4	Magnetic stirrer	Electrolab
5	Digimatic Caliper	Mitutoyo, Japan
6	Dissolution Apparatus	Electrolab TDT-08I plus
7	Infrared Spectrophotometer	FT-IR, Infinity, Shimadzu
8	UV/Vis Spectrophotometer	Shimadzu-1800
9	Texture Analyzer CT3	Brookfield
10	Incubator	Pathak electric work, Mumbai
11	Hot air oven	Pathak electric work, Mumbai
12	Digital analytical Balance	Redwag, LC-GC, Japan
13	Programmable Environmental Tester	Remielectrochemik, Pvt. Ltd, Vasai.
14	Disintegration test Apparatus	Electrolab
15	DSC	Mettler Toledo
16.	Dissolution Apparatus	Electro lab

3. METHODS

3.1 Solvent casting method:

Fast-dissolving film of Ropinirole HCl was prepared by the solvent-casting method. Solution I was prepared by dissolving the Ropinirole HCl in methanol. Solution II was prepared by dissolving the HPMC E-15, citric acid, polyethylene glycol-400 (PEG-400) in specific proportion, in distilled water.

Solution stirred on magnetic stirrer with addition of sweetener and flavouring agent up to three hours. Both solutions I and II were mixed and final solution set aside for remove air bubble. Then the mixture solution was casted onto a petri dish and it was dried in the oven at 60° C for 2 hours. The film was carefully removed from the petridish, checked for any imperfections, and cut according to the size required for testing (square film 2 cm length, 2 cm width). (Arya, A. et al., 2010)

Step-I Solution A –

Step-II Solution B –

Step-III –

Solution – A

Solution - B

4. Experimental work:

4.1 UV spectroscopy:

Ropinirole HCl is soluble in distilled water (DW) and Phosphate buffer pH 6.8 and sample solution of drug (5 to 25 μ g/ml) was prepared. Then the spectrum was scanned at range 200 to 400nm on UV spectrophotometer (Shimadzu-1800) and maximum

absorbance observed spectrum was compare with reported standard spectra of drug.

4.2 Differential scanning calorimetry: (DSC)

The thermal behavior of Ropinirole was examined by DSC. The DSC curve of the samples was obtained by a differential scanning calorimeter (Mettler Toledo). Each sample was placed in an aluminum pan and then

crimped with an aluminum cover. The heating and cooling rate were 20°C/min and all measurements were performed over temperature range 40–300 °C.

4.3 Fourier transforms infra-red spectroscopy:

The FTIR study of Ropinirole HCl was carried out to identify the functional group present in material. For FTIR spectroscopy, Ropinirole HCl was mixed with dried KBR in ratio 1:100. Then the IR spectrum was taken on FTIR spectrophotometer (IR Infinity, Shimadzu) by DRS technique.

4.4 Formulation and Development of placebo films:

Placebo mouth dissolving films were prepared by using novel film forming agent like HPMC E-15. Placebo film was prepared by solvent casting method and found to be idea film forming agent therefore selected for further formulation and development of MDF containing Ropinirole HCl for the treatment of Parkinson's disease.

4.5 Methodology in formulation of placebo film:

Variable quantities of HPMC E-15 are weighed accurately and dissolved in distilled water with addition of plasticizer. Stir on magnetic stirrer for 20 min and sonicate the solution for remove air bubbles and cast it in petri dish. On the basis result including appearance, better thickness and more transparency by visual observation F-3-(400 mg) is optimized concentration of polymer for solvent casting method.

5. Evaluation of Ropinirole MDF

In vitro disintegration test:

In vitro disintegration time was determined of Ropinirole HCl (MDF) in a petridish containing 10 ml

of water at 37° C. Each film was carefully positioned in the centre of the petridish and the time required for the MDF to completely disintegrate was noted (Yellanki S. K. *et al.*, 2012)

Drug Content uniformity

Drug content determination of the film was carried out by dissolving the film of 4 cm² in 100 ml of pH 6.8 phosphate buffer using magnetic stirrer for 1 hour. The drug concentration was then evaluated spectrophotometrically at λ_{max} of 249 nm. The determination was carried out in triplicate for all the formulations and average with standard deviation was recorded. (Bhyan Bhupindaret *et al.*, 2012)

Tensile properties:

Tensile strength

Tensile strength of Film was analyzed on tensile grip was fixed to the base of the Texture Analyzer, while the other one was attached to the load cell, sample was placed in between both tensile grips on the Texture Analyzer, Rupture force was taken as the maximum force required to break the sample and the tensile strength was calculated by the following equation. (HerreroA.M.*et al.*, 2007)

$$\text{Tensile strength} = \frac{\text{Rupture force}}{\text{Thickness} \times \text{width}}$$

Percentage elongation

Stress was applied, a strip sample stretches and this is referred as strain. Strain is basically the deformation of strip divided by original dimension of the sample. Generally elongation of strip increases as the plasticizer content increases. (Mishra R and Amin A. *et al.*, 2011)

$$\% \text{ Elongation} = \frac{\text{Increase in length of strip} - \text{Initial length of strip} \times 100}{\text{Initial length of strip}}$$

Folding endurance

Folding endurance was determined by repeated folding of the strip at the same place till the strip

breaks. The number of times the film was folded without breaking is computed as the folding endurance value. (Amin A. *et al.*, 2011)

In-vitro dissolution study

The dissolution study of all Ropinirole MDFs was determined in a dissolution apparatus (Electrolab TDT-08L plus) following the USP paddle method. All tests were conducted in 900 ml of phosphate buffer pH 6.8. The dissolution medium was maintained at a temperature of $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ with a paddle rotation speed at 50 rpm. Aliquots (5ml) were drawn at time intervals of 5 min. and maintained the sink condition by adding the fresh samples were immediately filtered through filter paper. The drug content was assessed spectrophotometrically (Shimadzu-1800 at λ_{max} 249 nm). The absorbance values were transformed to concentration by reference to a standard calibration curve obtained experimentally. (Arya A., *et al.*, 2010 and Sharma R.*et al.*, 2010).

Surface morphology study of MDF

Sample of mouth dissolving film prepared by fracturing the films in liquid nitrogen, mounted on

aluminum stubs, and sputter coated with platinum and surface morphology of MDF was studied by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with magnification of $\times 25,000$ (JEOL 5400, Tokyo, Japan). (Bhura N. *et al.*, 2012)

6. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

6.1 Identification Study of Drug

6.1.1 Ultra Violet Spectroscopy

Ropinirole HCl (10 mg) was dissolved in distilled water with concentrations $25 \mu\text{g/ml}$ & scanned at 400 nm to 200 nm; the UV spectrum of Ropinirole HCl shows prominent absorbance maxima at wavelength 249 nm Figure 1. These peaks are similar to the standard peaks, so confirmed identity of sample drug as Ropinirole HCl. Reported absorbance maxima of Ropinirole HCl was λ_{max} 250 nm.

Fig 1. UV Spectroscopy of Ropinirole HCl

6.1.2 DSC Study

DSC thermogram of pure drug as shown in figure 2 exhibited a sharp endothermic peak at 248.43°C . In

that neither peak nor a shift in DSC thermograms indicated absence of physical or chemical instabilities.

Figure 2. DSC of Ropinirole HCl

6.1.3 FTIR

FTIR spectra of Ropinirole shown in Figure 3. it is observed that, Peak of 1750 cm^{-1} confirms presence of C=O, sharp peak at 3053 cm^{-1} confirms the primary amide group, peak at 3153 cm^{-1} confirm the N-H bending and peak at 1421 confirms the CH_3 stretching in the structure of the drug given in figure 3.

FTIR study of Ropinirole HCl

Functional group	Range
N-H stretch	3053
N-H (bend)	3153
C=O	1750
CH ₃	1421

Figure 3. Infrared spectrum of Ropinirole HCl

Table 5. FTIR Study of HPMC E-15

Functional group	Range
O-H stretch	3498
C-H (bend)	3153

Figure. 4 Infrared spectrum of HPMC E-15

6.1.4 Melting Point

The melting point of the drug was found to be in the range 242-250°C and standard was reported 248°C and confirms the authentication.

6.1.5 Drug-excipient Interaction study

The drug-excipients intraction study was carried out by using FTIR spectroscopy. Study was carried for determination of chemical intraction between the functional groups of the drug and excipient. Study is

performed for determination of drug and excipients with each other.

6.1.6 Infrared Spectroscopy

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra of the Ropinirole HCl with polymer was observed in the range of 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} using a FTIR spectrophotometer (Shimadzu 8400S, Japan) by the DRS method as shown in figure 04. From above observation, it is clear that peak observed in pure drug from are stable in its physical mixture, hence it shows no intraction of drug with polymer mixture.

Figure 4. Ropinirole HCl + HPMC E-15 (Drug + Polymer)

Table 6. FTIR study of Ropinirole HCl + HPMC-E15

Functional group	Range	Observed peak in bulk	Observed peak in physical mixture	Inference
C=O	1730-1750cm	1750	1750	No interaction
N-H (stretch)	3100-3500	3153	3153	No interaction
N-H (bend)	1640-1550	1453	1453	No interaction

From above observation, it is clear that peak observed in pure drug form are stable in its physical mixture also, hence it shows no interaction of drug with excipients present in mixture.

6.1.7 Standard Calibration Curve

Standard calibration curve of Ropinirole HCl in distilled Water

The calibration curve for Ropinirole HCL in distilled water was found to be in the concentration range of 0.5 – 2.5 µg/ml and followed the Beer Lambert law.

Table 7. Standard calibration curve of Ropinirole HCl in distilled Water

Concentration (ppm)	Absorbance
0	0
5	0.242
10	0.464
15	0.691
20	0.937
25	1.157

$$\text{Equation: } y = 0.046x + 0.0003$$

$$R^2 = 0.999$$

Standard calibration curve of Ropinirole HCl in phosphate buffer (pH 6.8)

The calibration curve for Ropinirole HCl in phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) was found to be in the concentration range of 0.5–2.5 µg/ml and followed the Beer Lambert law. Calibration curve shown in figure 06.

Table 8. Standard calibration curve of Ropinirole HCl in 6.8 pH buffer

Concentration (ppm)	Absorbance
0	0
5	0.237
10	0.453
15	0.682
20	0.862
25	1.08

$$\text{Equation: } y = 0.042x + 0.016$$

$$R^2 = 0.998$$

Figure 6. Standard calibration curve of Ropinirole HCl in phosphate buffer (pH 6.8)

6.1.8 Evaluation of Trial Batches of HPMC E-15 series with PEG-400 as plasticizer

F1 to F4 formulations was prepared using HPMC E-15 polymers using plasticizer such as PEG 400. All these films were evaluated for appearance, disintegration time and Folding endurance.

Table 9. Evaluation of Trial Batches of HPMC E-15 with PEG-400

Sr. No.	Formulation	DT	Folding endurance	Appearance
1	F1	42	117	Transparent film
2	F2	34	160	Transparent film
3	F3	38	147	Transparent film
4	F4	39	156	Transparent film

All the films of F1 to F4 formulations were transparent. F2 batch was show good disintegration time as well as folding endurance.

6.1.9 Effect of Plasticizer

PEG 400 was used as a Plasticizer in films. All the films were transparent. As the concentration of

plasticizer increases it also increases the flexibility of the films. All the trial Batches were formulated using various proportion of plasticizer. Plasticizer also affects the film separation property of the film. F2 (conc. 0.7 ml) batch showed the good effect on folding endurance and Disintegration time. So, it was selected as a plasticizer concentration for further batches of the films.

6.1.10 Evaluation of MDF for solvent casting method

Table 10. Evaluation of MDF for solvent casting method

Batch No.	Weight Variation (mg) mean \pm S.D.	Thickness (mm) mean \pm S.D.	Folding Endurance mean \pm S.D.	D.T. (sec) mean \pm S.D.	% elongation mean \pm S.D.	Tensile Strength (gm/mm ²) mean \pm S.D.
F1	81 \pm 1.52	0.4 \pm 0.13	145 \pm 2.12	43 \pm 3.21	16.66 \pm 2.88	69.213 \pm 0.136
F2	84 \pm 2.15	0.3 \pm 0.01	154 \pm 1.732	40 \pm 0.577	16.66 \pm 5.773	71.6 \pm 0.173
F3	83 \pm 1.732	0.4 \pm 0.15	177 \pm 4.358	38 \pm 2.645	21.23 \pm 6.231	53.6 \pm 2.227
F4	78 \pm 1.52	0.2 \pm 0.17	135 \pm 1.732	41 \pm 3.605	36.666 \pm 7.637	55.713 \pm 0.5783
F5	80 \pm 1.26	0.3 \pm 0.05	115 \pm 3.464	42 \pm 2.645	40 \pm 5.235	71.83 \pm 0.3511
F6	87 \pm 0.57	0.4 \pm 0.17	168 \pm 2.081	35 \pm 3.511	33.33 \pm 2.8867	70.56 \pm 0.9
F7	90 \pm 1.73	0.3 \pm 0.11	133 \pm 2.812	43 \pm 2.081	11.66 \pm 5.773	74.13 \pm 0.927
F8	92 \pm 0.50	0.3 \pm 0.14	160 \pm 3.785	41 \pm 1.527	35 \pm 31.66	80.30 \pm 0.200
F9	93 \pm 1.16	0.4 \pm 0.13	173 \pm 3.605	36 \pm 1.154	72.5 \pm 8.66	58.32 \pm 1.119

*All values are expressed as mean \pm S.D. (n=3)

6.1.11 In-Vitro dissolution study

Table 11. In-vitro dissolution study

Time (min)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	53.23	49.33	50.25	51.25	53.65	58.58	49.56	49.23	48.245
10	64.35	62.56	64.57	61.54	62.25	66.24	56.13	58.21	55.14
15	75.36	72.24	77.56	70.21	74.25	80.32	71.25	67.15	67.88
20	84.23	81.35	82.36	80.21	82.24	87.56	79.35	79.25	76.32
25	90.56	89.54	89.25	89.25	90.54	92.54	86.14	86.24	84.24
30	92.35	93.78	93.25	94.25	95.24	97.66	93.25	92.47	91.25

*All values are expressed as mean \pm S.D. (n=3)

Figure 7. In-Vitro dissolution study (Batch No. F1-F3)

Figure 8. *In-Vitro* dissolution study (Batch No. F4-F6)

Figure 9 *In-Vitro* dissolution study (Batch No. F7-F9)

For solvent casting method, In vitro dissolution study of optimized batches as shown in (Fig. No.08 Casting F6) the all-batches release 49-97% drug in 5 to 30 min. The batch (F6) shows 97 % Drug release in 30 min. From the study it is conclude that the HPMC E 15 show good film forming property.

recorded result shown in table. (Bhyan Bhupindar *et al.*, 2012 and Patil *et al.*, 2014)

6.1.12 Drug Content

Drug content determination of the film was carried out by dissolving the film of 4 cm² in 100 ml of pH 6.8 phosphate buffer using magnetic stirrer for 1 hour. The drug concentration was then evaluated spectrophotometrically at λ_{max} of 249 nm. The determination was carried out in triplicate for all the formulations and average with standard deviation was

Table 12. Drug content

Batch code	% Drug content
F1	91.56 ± 1.23
F2	93.48 ± 1.84
F3	92.65 ± 2.47
F4	97.49 ± 1.82
F5	98.49 ± 1.54
F6	102.36 ± 1.87
F7	93.25 ± 0.79
F8	90.15 ± 2.45
F9	92.59 ± 1.25

*All values are expressed as mean ± S.D. (n=3)

6.1.13 Morphology Studies

Sample of mouth dissolving film prepared by fracturing the films in liquid nitrogen, mounted on aluminium stubs, and sputter coated with platinum

and surface morphology of MDF was studied by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with magnification of x 25,000 (JEOL 5400, Tokyo, Japan). (Bhura N. *et al.*, 2012)

Figure 10. SEM of MDFs of Ropinirole HCl

7. CONCLUSION:

The mouth dissolving film containing Ropinirole HCl was prepared by solvent casting method. HPMC E-15 used as film forming agent. The capacity of film forming is shown best by HPMC E-15. Because it shown film forming capacity in amount (400 mg) for solvent casting method. Increase the amount of film former shown increase the disintegration time and Tensile strength and decrease the concentration polymer then affect the strength of film. Therefore, the exact amount of film former and plasticizer

concentration is shown better result. When performing effect of plasticizer. The Tensile strength, percentage elongation increased with concentration of plasticizer, which produce soft film but simultaneously the disintegration time and dissolution time of film was increased. From the study, it can be concluded that the plasticizer PEG-400 is superior turn to disintegration and dissolution time and peel out property. Hence plasticizer (PEG-400) having short disintegration time and dissolution time with sufficient Tensile strength and percentage elongation. Without plasticizer film show more brittleness than it

is easy to break. Therefore, it is concluded that the formulation of Ropinirole HCl was successfully formulated and it was showing result.

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